

Supporting information

Mechanochemical Fluorescence Switching in Polymers containing Dithiomaleimide Moieties

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Table of Contents

Experimental section.....	2
NMR spectra	7
Mass spectra	16
Sonication experiments Poly(methyl acrylate)	18
Experiments to identify the product produced by mechanochemical activation of the DTM motif	22
Sonication experiments Poly(ϵ -caprolactone)	24
References	30

Experimental section

Materials

Unless otherwise stated, all reagents and solvents were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich and used without further purification. ϵ -Caprolactone was dried over calcium hydride and purified by distillation under reduced pressure and was stored in a glovebox under nitrogen. Unless otherwise noted, all reactions were carried out under ambient atmosphere. 3-Bromo-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione was synthesized as previously reported.¹ The reference PMA was provided by Michela Di Giannantonio and synthesized as previously reported.²

Instrumentation

NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Avance III or Avance III HD spectrometers at 400 MHz (¹H) and 100 MHz (¹³C), respectively. Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million (ppm) relative to TMS, although referencing was done based on residual solvent protons. Flash silica gel column chromatography was carried out with a Biotage Isolera Flash system using Biotage Flash Cartridges. Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) experiments were performed on an Agilent 1200 series HPLC system equipped with an Agilent PLgel mixed guard column (particle size = 5 μ m) and two Agilent PLgel mixed-D columns (ID = 7.5 mm, L = 300 mm, particle size = 5 μ m). Signals were recorded by a UV detector (Agilent 1200 series), an Optilab REX interferometric refractometer, and a miniDawn TREOS light scattering detector (Wyatt Technology Corp.). Samples were run using THF as the eluent at 30 °C and a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Data analyses were done on Astra software (Wyatt Technology Corp.) and molecular weights were determined based on narrow-molecular-weight polystyrene calibration (from 2,340 to 364,000 g/mol). Emission spectra were recorded on a PTI C720 fluorescence spectrometer using right angle illumination. For excitation, a XeArc lamp was used along with a PETI 814 photomultiplier detection system. Ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectra were

recorded on a Shimadzu UV-2401PC spectrophotometer. Sonication experiments were performed using a Branson Model 450 ultrasonic horn sonicator equipped with a 13 mm sonicator tip. A VWR MX07R-20 refrigerating/heating bath was used to maintain a constant solution temperature during sonication experiments. Elemental analyses (EA) were performed on a CE Instruments EA 1110 by flash combustion and GC separation.

Synthesis of 1-benzyl-3,4-dibromo-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione (1)

In a 100 mL round-bottom flask (RBF) 2,3-dibromomaleimide (2.65 g, 10.4 mmol) and potassium carbonate (1.73 g, 12.4 mmol) were dissolved in acetone (50 mL). Benzyl bromide (1.5 mL, 12.6 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. EtOAc (250 mL) was added and the organic layer was washed with water (400 mL) before it was dried over MgSO₄, filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. The product was purified by flash column chromatography (SiO₂, hexane:EtOAc, elution gradient 10-30% EtOAc) which, after solvent removal and drying in a vacuum oven at 40 °C overnight, afforded **1** (2.67 g, 7.7 mmol, 74%) as an off-white powder.

¹H NMR (CD₂Cl₂, ppm): δ = 4.80 (2H, s), 7.39 (5H, m); ¹³C NMR (CD₂Cl₂, ppm): δ = 43.61, 128.69, 128.97, 129.27, 129.97, 136.01, 164.19; MS (EI) *m/z* [M + H⁺] calcd. for (C₁₁H₇Br₂NO₂) 344.88, found 345.1; EA calcd. for C₁₁H₇Br₂NO₂: C = 38.30%; H = 2.05%; N = 4.06%; found: C = 38.70% H = 2.00% N = 3.73%.

Synthesis of 1-benzyl-3,4-bis(2-hydroxyethylthio)-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione (2)

In a 50 mL RBF compound **1** (1.31 g, 3.8 mmol) and imidazole (0.65 g, 9.5 mmol) were dissolved in THF (15 mL). Mercaptoethanol (0.67 mL, 9.5 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at room temperature; a precipitate formed during the reaction. EtOAc (200 mL) was added and the organic layer was washed with water (2 x 200 mL) before it was dried over MgSO₄, filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. The product was purified by flash

column chromatography (SiO₂, dichloromethane:methanol, elution gradient 0-5% methanol) which, after solvent removal and drying in a vacuum oven at 40 °C overnight, afforded **2** (0.74 g, 2.2 mmol, 57%) as a yellow oil.

¹H NMR (CD₂Cl₂, ppm): δ = 3.46 (4H, t), 3.82 (4H, t), 4.66 (2H, s), 7.32 (5H, m); ¹³C NMR (CD₂Cl₂, ppm): δ = 34.80, 42.45, 62.19, 128.11, 128.51, 128.90, 136.03, 136.53, 166.43; MS (ESI) *m/z* [M + Na⁺] calc. for (C₁₅H₁₇NNaO₄S₂) 362.05, found 362.00; EA calcd. for C₁₅H₁₇NO₄S₂: C = 53.80%; H = 5.05%; N = 4.13%; found, C = 53.24%; H = 5.08%; N = 4.73%.

Synthesis of ((1-benzyl-2,5-dioxo-2,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrrole-3,4-diyl)bis(sulfanediyl))bis(ethane-2,1-diyl) bis(2-bromo-2-methylpropanoate) (3)

A dry 10 mL RBF was charged with compound **2** (134 mg, 0.39 mmol) and three evacuation/argon cycles were performed before dry THF (5 mL) and dry TEA (0.14 mL, 1.00 mmol, 2.5 eq) were added. Subsequently a solution of α-bromoisobutyryl bromide (0.12 mL, 0.97 mmol, 2.5 eq) in dry THF (5 mL) was added dropwise under stirring and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature overnight. DCM (100 mL) was added and the organic layer was washed with sodium carbonate (100 mL) before it was dried over MgSO₄, filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. The product was purified by flash column chromatography (SiO₂, Hexane:DCM, elution gradient 50-90% DCM) which, after solvent removal and drying in a vacuum oven at 40°C overnight, afforded **3** (200 mg, 0.31 mmol, 79%) as a yellow oil.

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, ppm): δ = 1.90 (12H, t), 3.61 (4H, t), 4.40 (4H, t), 4.65 (2H, s), 7.34 (5H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, ppm): δ = 30.08, 30.84, 42.50, 55.48, 59.67, 63.99, 65.02, 128.16, 128.72, 128.93, 129.18, 134.43, 135.12, 135.99, 165.97, 170.51, 171.30, 171.48; MS (ESI) *m/z* [M + Na⁺] calcd. for (C₂₃H₂₇Br₂NO₆S₂) 659.9, found 659.9; EA calcd. for C₂₃H₂₇Br₂NO₆S₂: C = 43.34%; H = 4.27%; N = 2.20%; found, C = 43.2%; H = 4.3%; N = 2.3%.

Synthesis of 3-((2-hydroxyethyl)thio)-1*H*-pyrrole-2,5-dione (5)

In a 50 mL RBF 3-bromo-1*H*-pyrrole-2,5-dione (300 mg, 1.7 mmol) and imidazole (116mg, 1.7 mmol) were dissolved in THF (4 mL). Mercaptoethanol (0.15 mL, 2.1 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h. EtOAc (50 mL) was added and the organic layer was washed with water (3x50 mL) before it was dried over MgSO₄, filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. The product was purified by flash column chromatography (SiO₂, Hexane:EtOAc, elution gradient 30-80% EtOAc) which, after solvent removal and drying in a vacuum oven at 40°C overnight, afforded **5** (71 mg, 0.4 mmol, 24%) as a yellow oil.

¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆, ppm): δ = 3.08 (2H, t), 3.66 (2H, t), 5.06 (1H, t), 6.43 (1H, s), 10.92 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-d₆, ppm): δ = 34.26, 58.50, 119.25, 150.85, 169.32, 170.97; MS (ESI) *m/z* [M + Na⁺] calcd. for (C₆H₇NO₃S) 196.01, found 196.4; EA calcd. for C₆H₇NO₃S: C = 41.61%; H = 4.07%; N = 8.09%; found, C = 41.5%; H = 4.1%; N = 8.0%.

Synthesis of 1-benzyl-3-((2-hydroxyethyl)thio)-1*H*-pyrrole-2,5-dione (**4**)

In a 10 mL RBF compound **5** (50 mg, 0.3 mmol) and potassium carbonate (48 mg, 0.3 mmol) were dissolved in acetone (3 mL). Benzyl bromide (41 μL, 0.3 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature overnight. EtOAc (50 mL) was added and the organic layer was washed with water (3x50 mL) before it was dried over MgSO₄, filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. The product was purified by flash column chromatography (SiO₂, hexane:EtOAc, elution gradient 3-60% EtOAc) which, after solvent removal and drying in a vacuum oven at 40°C overnight, afforded **4** (28 mg, 0.1 mmol, 74%) as a yellow oil.

¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆, ppm): δ = 3.13 (2H, t), 3.67 (2H, t), 4.59 (1H, t), 5.08 (1H, s), 6.63 (1H, s), 7.27 (5H, m); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-d₆, ppm): δ = 34.33, 40.85, 58.45, 118.40, 127.25, 127.41, 128.57, 136.64, 150.67, 167.67, 169.28; MS (ESI) *m/z* [M + Na⁺] calcd. for

(C₁₃H₁₃NO₃S) 286.06, found 286.1; EA calcd. for C₁₃H₁₃NO₃S: C = 59.30%; H = 4.98%; N = 5.32%; found, C = 59.4%; H = 4.8%; N = 5.4%.

General procedure for the synthesis of PMA-DTM

Compound **3** (8 mg, 0.01 mmol) and Cu(0) (3 mg, 0.05 mmol) were introduced into a 10 mL Schlenk flask and degassed by three cycles of evacuation and filling with argon. A solution of Me₆TREN (10 μL, 0.04 mmol) in dry DMSO (2 mL) and methyl acrylate (2 mL, 22.00 mmol), which had previously been sparged with argon for 15 min, were added and three freeze-pump-thaw cycles were performed. The polymerization mixture was then stirred at room temperature for 1 h. To quench the reaction, the Schlenk flask was opened and placed in liquid nitrogen. The reaction mixture was subsequently dissolved in THF (20 mL) and filtered through a short silica pad before the product was precipitated in cold methanol (500 mL). The polymer was re-dissolved in THF (20 mL) and precipitated again in cold methanol (500 mL). The product was filtered off, dried in a vacuum oven at 40°C overnight and a yellow sticky solid was obtained (454 mg).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ = 1.4-2 (2H, m), 2.31 (1H, m), 3.66 (3H, s); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃): δ = 35.11, 41.47, 51.85, 175.03; SEC *M_n* = 106.6 kg/mol, *D* = 1.45; EA calcd. for (C₄H₆O₂)₁₂₀₀ + C₂₃H₂₇Br₂NO₆S₂: C = 55.74%, H = 7.01%, N = 0.01%; found: C = 55.9%, H = 7.2%.

General procedure for the synthesis of PCL-DTM

Compound **2** (10 mg, 0.03 mmol) was introduced into a 10 mL Schlenk flask and degassed by three cycles of evacuation and filling with nitrogen. ε-Caprolactone (2.5 mL, 22.6 mmol) was added under nitrogen and the stirred reaction mixture was heated to 110 °C. Two drops of tin(II) 2-ethylhexanoate were added and the reaction was stirred overnight at 110 °C. To quench

the reaction, the Schlenk flask was opened and placed in a freezer for 10 min. The reaction mixture was subsequently dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (40 mL) and precipitated in cold diethyl ether (400 mL). The polymer was re-dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (40 mL) and precipitated again in cold diethyl ether (400 mL). The product was filtered off, dried in a vacuum oven at 40°C overnight and a filamentous yellow solid was obtained (1.8 g).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ = 1.38 (1H, m), 1.65 (2H, m), 2.30 (1H, t), 4.05 (1H, t); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃): δ = 24.73, 25.68, 28.50, 34.27, 64.29, 173.68; SEC M_n = 72.3 kg/mol, D = 1.42; EA calcd. for (C₆H₁₀O₂)₆₃₀ + C₁₅H₁₇NO₄S₂: C = 63.09%, H = 8.81%, N = 0.02%; found: C = 62.9%, H = 8.9%.

General procedure for the sonication experiments

The polymer (15 mg) was dissolved in 1,4-dioxane (20 mL) by stirring for 30 min. The solution (18 mL) was transferred into a Suslick cell, which was placed into a cryostat maintained at 20 °C, and degassed by sparging with nitrogen for 20 min. The polymer solution was then submitted to pulsed ultrasound with an on period of 0.5 s, an off period of 1 s, and an intensity of 10.4 W/cm², with an internal temperature fluctuating between 20-22°C. Aliquots of 300 μL were removed after 0, 10, 20, 30, 45, 60, 90, 120, 180, 240, and 300 min, diluted with 1,4-dioxane (300 μL each), and the fluorescence spectra of the samples were recorded. The solvent was subsequently removed by drying in a vacuum oven at 40°C overnight and the residues were dissolved in THF (300 μL) to allow SEC analyses.

NMR spectra

1-Benzyl-3,4-dibromo-1*H*-pyrrole-2,5-dione (1)

Figure S1: ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **1** in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S2: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **1** in CD_2Cl_2 .

1-Benzyl-3,4-bis(2-hydroxyethylthio)-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione (2)

Figure S3: ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **2** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S4: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **2** in CDCl_3 .

((1-Benzyl-2,5-dioxo-2,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrrole-3,4-diyl)bis(sulfanediyl))bis(ethane-2,1-diyl) bis(2-bromo-2-methylpropanoate) (**3**)

Figure S5: ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **3** in CDCl_3 .

Figure S6: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **3** in CDCl_3 .

3-((2-Hydroxyethyl)thio)-1*H*-pyrrole-2,5-dione (**4**)

Figure S7: ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **5** in DMSO- d_6 .

Figure S8: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **5** in DMSO- d_6 .

1-Benzyl-3-((2-hydroxyethyl)thio)-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione (5**)**

Figure S9: ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **4** in DMSO- d_6 .

Figure S10: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **4** in DMSO- d_6 .

PMA-DTM

Figure S11: ^1H NMR spectrum of PMA-DTM in CDCl_3 .

Figure S12: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of PMA-DTM in CDCl_3 .

PCL-DTM

Figure S13: ¹H NMR spectrum of high-*M_n* PCL-DTM in CDCl₃.

Figure S14: ¹³C NMR spectrum of high-*M_n* PCL-DTM in CDCl₃.

Figure S15: ^1H NMR spectrum of low- M_n PCL-DTM in CDCl_3 .

Figure S16: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of low- M_n PCL-DTM in CDCl_3 .

Mass spectra

1-Benzyl-3,4-dibromo-1*H*-pyrrole-2,5-dione (1)

Figure S17: Electron impact mass spectrum of compound 1.

1-Benzyl-3,4-bis(2-hydroxyethylthio)-1*H*-pyrrole-2,5-dione (2)

Figure S18: Electrospray ionization mass spectrum of compound 2.

((1-Benzyl-2,5-dioxo-2,5-dihydro-1H-pyrrole-3,4-diyl)bis(sulfanediyl))bis(ethane-2,1-diyl) bis(2-bromo-2-methylpropanoate) (3)

Figure S19: Electrospray ionization mass spectrum of compound **3**.

3-((2-Hydroxyethyl)thio)-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione (5)

Figure S20: Electrospray ionization mass spectrum of compound **5**.

1-Benzyl-3-((2-hydroxyethyl)thio)-1*H*-pyrrole-2,5-dione (**4**)

Figure S21: Electrospray ionization mass spectrum of compound **4**.

Sonication experiments Poly(methyl acrylate)

Figure S22: Representative size-exclusion chromatograms (UV absorbance signals at 405 nm) of PMA-DTM upon ultrasonication of a dilute 1,4-dioxane solution ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) for the times indicated.

Figure S23: Evolution of $M_n/M_{n,0}$ upon ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) of PMA-DTM. The graph shows data from three separate experiments.

Figure S24: Evolution of the normalized fluorescence emission intensity at 525 nm ($\lambda_{ex} = 405$ nm) upon ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) of PMA-DTM. The graph shows data from three separate experiments.

Figure S25: Representative size-exclusion chromatograms (refractive index signals) upon ultrasonication of a dilute dioxane solution ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) of PMA for the times indicated.

Figure S26: Evolution of $M_n/M_{n,0}$ upon ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions ($c=0.75$ mg/mL) of PMA. The graph shows data from three separate experiments.

Figure S27: Kinetic plot of the SEC results during the first hour of ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions of PMA-DTM and PMA ($c = 0.75 \text{ mg/mL}$). The graph shows datapoints from three separate experiments and linear fits as plain line.

Figure S28: Representative fluorescence emission spectra recorded upon ultrasonication of a dilute 1,4-dioxane solution of PMA ($c = 0.75 \text{ mg/mL}$) and compound **3** ($c = 7.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol.L}^{-1}$) for the times indicated. $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405 \text{ nm}$.

Figure S29: Evolution of the normalized fluorescence emission intensity at 525 nm ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405$ nm) upon ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions of PMA ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) and compound **3** ($c = 7.0 \times 10^{-6}$ mol.L⁻¹) for the times indicated. The graph shows data from three separate experiments.

Experiments to identify the product produced by mechanochemical activation of the DTM motif

In order to identify the product(s) produced by mechanochemical activation of the DTM motif via ultrasonication of polymer solutions, sonication experiments with a higher concentration of PMA-DTM ($c = 2$ mg/mL) were carried out. The resulting solution was concentrated and precipitated into cold methanol before characterization. The UV-vis absorption spectrums of the re-dissolved material (**Figure S28**) reveals a small shift of the absorption maximum, but the spectrum does not match that of reference compound **4**. The sample was also characterized by ¹H NMR spectroscopy (**Figure S29**) but no proton at 6.63 ppm, characteristic of compound **4**, could be observed with 500 scans acquired.

Figure S30: UV-vis absorption spectra of a dilute 1,4-dioxane solution of PMA-DTM ($c = 2$ mg/mL) before (black) and upon ultrasonication for 5h (red).

Figure S31: ^1H NMR spectra (500 scans) DMSO- d_6 of a dilute 1,4-dioxane solution of PMA-DTM ($c = 2$ mg/mL) upon ultrasonication for 5h. Inset shows an expanded view of the region between 7.5 and 4.5 ppm.

Sonication experiments Poly(ϵ -caprolactone)

Figure S32: Evolution of $M_n/M_{n,0}$ upon ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) of high- M_n PCL-DTM. The graph shows data from three separate experiments.

Figure S33: Evolution of the normalized fluorescence emission intensity at 525 nm ($\lambda_{ex} = 405$ nm) upon ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) of high- M_n PCL-DTM. The graph shows data from three separate experiments.

Figure S34: Representative size-exclusion chromatograms (UV absorbance signals at 405 nm) upon ultrasonication of a dilute 1,4-dioxane solution ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) of high- M_n PCL-DTM for the times indicated.

Figure S35: Evolution of $M_n/M_{n,0}$ upon ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) of low- M_n PCL-DTM. The graph shows data from three separate experiments.

Figure S36: Representative size-exclusion chromatograms (refractive index signals) upon ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solution solution ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) of low- M_n PCL-DTM for the times indicated.

Figure S37: Representative fluorescence emission spectra recorded upon ultrasonication of a dilute 1,4-dioxane solution ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) of low- M_n PCL-DTM for the times indicated. $\lambda_{ex} = 405$ nm.

Figure S38: Evolution of the normalized fluorescence emission intensity at 540 nm ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405$ nm) upon ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) of low- M_n PCL-DTM. The graph shows data from three separate experiments.

Figure S39: Representative size-exclusion chromatograms (refractive index signals) upon ultrasonication of a dilute 1,4-dioxane solution containing PCL ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) and compound **2** ($c = 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$ mol.L $^{-1}$) for the times indicated.

Figure S40: Evolution of $M_n/M_{n,0}$ upon ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions containing PCL ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL) and compound **2** ($c = 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$ mol.L⁻¹). The graph shows data from three separate experiments.

Figure S41: Kinetic plot of the SEC results during the first hour of ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions of High Mn PCL-DTM and PCL ($c = 0.75$ mg/mL). The graph shows datapoints from three separate experiments and linear fits as plain line.

Figure S42: Representative fluorescence emission spectra recorded upon ultrasonication of a dilute 1,4-dioxane solution containing a mixture of PCL ($c = 0.75 \text{ mg/mL}$) and compound **2** ($c = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol.L}^{-1}$) for the times indicated. $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405 \text{ nm}$.

Figure S43: Evolution of the normalized fluorescence emission intensity at 540 nm ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405 \text{ nm}$) upon ultrasonication of dilute 1,4-dioxane solutions containing a mixture of PCL ($c = 0.75 \text{ mg/mL}$) and compound **2** ($c = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol.L}^{-1}$). The graph shows data from three separate experiments.

References

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